

Effect of Temperature on the Conductance of Chloramine-T and Bromamine-T in different Compositions of Solvent Mixtures

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The conductance behaviour of chloramine-T (CAT) and bromamine-T (BAT) has been studied as a function of temperature in different compositions of water-methanol and water-ethanol (v/v). The measured molar conductance under different conditions has been analysed by Debye-Hückel-Onsager theory of conductivity. These values have been used to compute molar conductance at infinite dilution, dissociation constant, energy of activation of the rate process and thermodynamic parameters. Viscosity of CAT and BAT in different composition of solvent mixture at various temperatures is determined and hence Walden product ($\lambda_m^0 \eta_0$) under these conditions has been calculated. These computed values have been used to discuss qualitatively the nature of the ion-solvent and solvent-solvent interactions of CAT/BAT with water, alcohol and their mixtures.

Selective solvation of ions in binary solvent mixtures involving protic and dipolar aprotic solvent is of considerable importance, both from a fundamental^{1,2} and a technological point of view³. The conductometric method is well known to give valuable information regarding ion-solvent interaction. Conductance studies of electrolytes in mixed solvents has received considerable attention in recent years^{4,5}. It has also been found that the dielectric constant of the medium plays a very important role concerning the behaviour of electrolytes in solutions.

The sodium salt of *N*-chloro/*N*-bromotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide, i.e. chloramine-T (CAT) and bromamine-T (BAT) are well-known as oxidimetric analytical reagents, and can be used in the place of more expensive iodine solution^{6,7}. These electrolytes can be used as oxidants in the kinetic and mechanistic studies of some substrates⁸. But there are no reports on the transport properties of either CAT or BAT except for one titrimetric work with CAT⁹. Hence the present investigation was undertaken on the transport properties of CAT and BAT in different solvent mixtures as a function of temperature and the results are reported here in continuation of the previous work on the conductance behaviour of CAT and BAT¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

Molar conductivity : Specific conductances (k) of

CAT in water-methanol and water-ethanol and BAT in water-methanol at different compositions (v/v) and temperatures were noted after proper correction for solvent conductance¹¹. Molar conductance (λ_m) values were calculated. Molar conductance at infinite dilution (λ_m^0) was computed from Onsager plot and hence obtained values are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

As expected, limiting molar conductance increased with the increase in temperature at every compositions of water-methanol/ethanol in both the cases of electrolytes (CAT and BAT) indicating less solvation or higher mobility of available ions or even the increase in number of ions due to higher frequency and bond-breaking at higher temperatures. The observed variation in λ_m with solvent composition may be explained as follows. The three-dimensional structures of water gets disturbed with the addition of organic solvent due to hydrophobic interaction of CH₃ group in CH₃OH or C₂H₅OH, or alternately that the addition of co-solvent to water results in a competition for H-bonding with water by anions and co-solvent¹², and as a result some water molecules are removed from the solvation shell of anions. This decreases the size of the solvation shell thereby increasing the conductivity. But the transfer process is obviously difficult in CH₃OH-H₂O or C₂H₅OH-H₂O mixture as the holes of three-dimensional structure may be blocked by water-alcohol com-

TABLE 1 – CALCULATED MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AT INFINITE DILUTION FROM λ_m VS \sqrt{C} PLOT FOR CAT IN VARIOUS WATER-METHANOL AND WATER-ETHANOL MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

T K	λ_m° ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)							
	0%	10%	20%	40%	50%	60%	80%	100%
Water-methanol								
303	78.00	66.80	68.60	51.00	57.00	61.00	63.20	89.75
308	89.50	76.00	85.00	107.00	80.50	67.50	74.00	98.50
313	98.00	98.50	115.00	140.00	110.00	90.00	88.00	107.00
318	104.00	127.00	131.00	179.00	170.00	130.00	101.50	113.80
Water-ethanol								
303	78.00	79.50	61.00	46.50	34.00	29.00	25.00	133.33
308	89.50	95.00	81.00	60.00	45.00	34.00	29.00	144.93
313	98.00	103.00	97.50	84.00	84.00	39.00	37.50	190.48
318	104.00	116.00	122.00	104.00	114.00	49.00	40.00	—

TABLE 2 – CALCULATED MOLAR CONDUCTANCES AT INFINITE DILUTION FROM λ_m VS \sqrt{C} PLOT FOR BAT IN VARIOUS WATER-METHANOL MIXTURES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

T K	λ_m° ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)							
	0%	10%	20%	30%	40%	60%	80%	100%
303	200.00	125.00	117.00	89.00	95.00	94.00	87.00	198.00
308	205.00	148.00	135.00	115.50	118.00	125.00	97.00	227.00
313	234.00	176.00	152.00	144.00	151.50	170.00	110.00	248.00
318	—	183.00	177.00	175.00	178.00	217.00	127.00	274.50

plex or only alcohol (MeOH or EtOH) species, and the structure-making or -breaking would be a slow process and hence conductivity decreases.

As expected conductivity increases with increasing temperature because of higher mobility of the ion, which is due to increase in thermal energy and breaking of higher number of hydrogen bonds. Even the vibrational, rotational and translational energy also vary with temperature. Because of these, the magnitude of variation of conductivity with temperature is different when one moves from low to high temperature. The solvent affects conductance primarily through its viscosity, hydrogen bonding capability, dielectric constant and its specific interaction with ions. Further, solvent viscosity resists the motion of ions, and the dielectric properties of the solvent control the effective field strength and inter-ionic potential. These

affect not only ionic viscosity but also the attraction between ions and consequently the extent of pairing. Specific solvation of ions can affect both mobility and association.

Chloramine-T gives⁷ different species at different pH. As the pH increases the anion RNCl /Br assumes importance and is present in a reasonably high concentration even in a weakly acidic solution. In strong acid medium the free acid and toluene-*p*-sulphonamide predominate. This phenomena was proved by Higuchi *et al.*¹³. It is also proposed^{12,13} that when methanol or ethanol is added to water the pH of the mixture varies slowly and becomes even less than that of the pure solvent at about 60% of methanol or ethanol. Since species of chloramine-T (even the concentration of the species) varies⁷ with pH, the solution mobility and conductivity also vary. Therefore for the variation of

conductivity with composition and temperature, it is too difficult to assign any specific reason except for a combined effect.

Chloramine-T and bromamine-T ionises⁷ in solvent and attain equilibrium as

where α is the degree of ionisation ($\alpha = \lambda_m/\lambda_m^0$). On substitution the value in the equation for dissociation constant,

$$K = \frac{\alpha^2 C}{1-\alpha} \quad (2)$$

where activity coefficient is being taken as unity. K , so obtained is used for the calculation of thermodynamic parameters. The variation of K with percentage composition and temperature is due to the selective solvation of the ion by the solvent. The decrease or increase in the values of dissociation constant with increase in temperature (values not shown) indicates the endothermic or exothermic nature of the dissociation process of the salt in solvent as well as in solvent mixtures. The variation in the values of K with composition is primarily due to change in dielectric constant, and it also indicates that the electrolyte causes a reduction in the thickness of the ionic environment surrounding ionic species. It may reduce the repulsion between different ionic species by increasing the aggregation number capacity. It may also, due to bulky organic molecules, either enter the solvation shell or come out of it during the movement of the solvated ion in the bulk of the solution.

Thermodynamic parameters : The conductance of an ion depends on its rate of movement, and hence it is quite reasonable¹⁴ to treat conductance similar to the one that employed for the process taking place at a definite rate which increases with temperature, i.e.

$$\lambda_m^0 = A e^{-E_a/RT} \quad (3)$$

or

$$\log \lambda_m^0 = \log A - E_a/2.303 RT \quad (4)$$

where A is a constant and E_a the activation energy of the rate process which determines the rate of movement of ions in solution. From the plot of $\log \lambda_m^0$ vs $1/T$ for all compositions for CAT and BAT, the E_a values (from the slope) are computed (Tables 3 and 4). E_a increased in the beginning, with the addition of methanol or ethanol to water, till 40% of methanol (upto 50% of ethanol with CAT) and decreased slowly on further additions of methanol or ethanol.

The heat of dissociation (ΔH°) is obtained from the slope of the plot of $\log K$ vs $1/T$. Free energy for the dissociation process (ΔG°) is calculated from the equation,

$$\Delta G^\circ = -2.303 RT \log K \quad (6)$$

Finally the entropy change (ΔS°) is calculated from the relation,

$$\Delta S^\circ = (\Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ)/T \quad (7)$$

The average values of ΔH° , ΔG° and ΔS° are given in Tables 3 and 4 for CAT and BAT respectively.

The change in enthalpy for CAT in water-methanol is exothermic for all compositions with a minimum around 40% methanol, and in water-ethanol minimum is found around 50% ethanol after showing endothermic character around 10–20%. But for BAT in water-methanol exothermic nature is found only at 0 and 100% of co-solvent, and endothermic behaviour for the rest of the composition with a maximum at 40% ethanol. The minimum of enthalpy of solution may be due to the preferential hydration¹⁵ of ions, or due to the formation of some complexes from molecules of organic co-solvent and water with a cation or even with both ions. It may also be thought that co-solvent species form mixed associates with water which affects the association enthalpies of electrolyte. The middle range of organic co-solvent contents, hydrophobic effects are minimum and changes in the equilibria of aggregates formed by hydrogen bonds occur continuously. Alternatively, entities containing molecules form both the substances linked by hydrogen bonds may also be formed.

TABLE 3 – COMPUTED THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR CAT UNDER VARYING COMPOSITIONS OF WATER-METHANOL AND WATER-ETHANOL MIXTURES

Parameter	0%	10%	20%	40%	50%	60%	80%	100%
Water-methanol								
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	12.76	35.10	38.29	61.27	60.63	53.61	23.51	5.21
ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-8.30	-42.35	-32.25	-95.74	-45.95	-89.35	-59.57	-19.15
ΔS° (kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-0.032 8	-0.157 9	-0.123 7	-0.325 9	-0.169 7	-0.325 1	-0.216 3	-0.090 4
ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	1.77	5.53	5.22	3.01	5.48	9.14	5.98	8.61
Water-ethanol								
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	12.76	19.15	43.76	44.68	65.65	29.78	30.64	22.02
ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-8.30	76.59	24.37	-25.53	-76.59	-25.53	-27.66	-10.72
ΔS° (kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-0.032 8	0.227 0	0.059 5	-0.105 8	-0.264 9	0.102 1	-0.109 7	-0.070 3
ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	1.77	7.82	6.34	6.53	3.66	5.41	5.59	10.89

TABLE 4 – COMPUTED THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR BAT IN WATER-METHANOL MIXTURE AT DIFFERENT COMPOSITION

Parameter	0%	10%	20%	30%	40%	50%	60%	100%
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	11.60	25.53	21.27	35.90	34.19	53.61	17.95	15.50
ΔH° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	-306.14	-54.71	38.29	27.35	47.13	10.94	7.05	-264.52
ΔS° (kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-0.010 6	-0.198 8	9.102 4	0.073 4	0.131 1	0.010 0	-0.003 8	-0.089 5
ΔG° (kJ mol ⁻¹)	18.62	5.53	7.26	5.11	7.42	7.90	8.19	10.59

The small and negative entropy of dissociation in all cases except from 20 to 50% of methanol for BAT in water-ethanol (where it is small positive) suggests that the specific interaction requires steric restriction for the formation of contact ion-pairs or ionic association. Of all thermodynamic functions describing solvation or solvation process, entropy is significantly connected with the solvent structure perturbations brought about by the dissolved ions. The calculated free energy change of dissociation in all the cases is slightly positive. It requires much more data to interpret the proper solvation dynamics.

Walden product: Walden product of an ion or a solute is inversely proportional to the effective radius of ion or solute in a given solvent or solvent mixture¹⁶. This product relates molar conductance at infinite dilution to viscosity (η_0) of the solvent as

$$\lambda_m^\circ \eta_0 = \frac{ze_o F}{6 \pi r T} \quad (9)$$

If the radius of the ion (r) is the same in every solvent or solvent mixture, the product is also constant. Variations

of density and viscosity for CAT and BAT at different temperatures and percentage compositions of water-alcohol are shown in Tables 5 and 6. The higher the viscosity, lesser will be the mobility of ions in that solution. It is seen (Tables 1 and 5) that this principle is not fully valid for CAT in water-alcohol mixture, whereas BAT in water-methanol almost follows the theory (Tables 2 and 6).

The variation of Walden product with dielectric constant (i.e. the variation of solvent composition) is somewhat complex. The Walden product increased with the increase in temperature for CAT and BAT in water-alcohol binary mixtures at all compositions (Tables 5 and 6). There is no regular expected trend either in the case of CAT in water-methanol or BAT in water-methanol at different compositions of solvent mixtures (Tables 5 and 6). As can be seen from these tables, the product increases sharply as soon as the non-aqueous solvent (co-solvent) is added to an aqueous solvent, due to solvent-solvent interaction, in both the cases. A sharp increase is found at 100% ethanol, whereas it decreased in methanol for CAT and BAT, and in between these two compositions the variation of Walden

TABLE 6 – OBSERVED DENSITY, VISCOSITY AND CALCULATED WALDEN PRODUCT FOR BAT IN WATER-METHANOL MIXTURE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND COMPOSITIONS

T K	0%			10%			20%			30%		
	$\lambda_m^o \eta_o$	d	$\eta_o \times 10^{-2}$ poise	$\lambda_m^o \eta_o$	d	$\eta_o \times 10^{-2}$ poise	$\lambda_m^o \eta_o$	d	$\eta_o \times 10^{-2}$ poise	$\lambda_m^o \eta_o$	d	$\eta_o \times 10^{-2}$ poise
303	1.595	0.983 5	0.912 6	1.141	0.969 9	1.023	1.197	0.958 9	1.142	1.017		
308	1.475	0.985 4	0.859 7	1.272	0.968 4	0.979 3	1.322	0.957 8	1.054	1.217		
313	1.528	0.990 9	0.776 7	1.367	0.964 9	0.887 0	1.348	0.955 7	0.971 1	1.398		
318	–	0.987 3	0.696 4	1.274	0.967 0	0.782 1	1.384	0.954 5	0.825 9	1.445		
		40%			50%			60%			100%	
		d	η_o	$\lambda_m^o \eta_o$	d	η_o	$\lambda_m^o \eta_o$	d	η_o	$\lambda_m^o \eta_o$	$\lambda_m^o \eta_o$	
303	0.968 9	1.278	1.214	0.931 4	1.264	1.189	0.913 4	1.213	1.056	1.041*		
308	0.966 7	1.208	1.425	0.929 5	1.198	1.498	0.911 3	1.138	1.104	1.076		
313	0.964 6	1.073	1.626	0.924 4	1.073	1.825	0.934 5	1.058	1.164	1.114		
318	0.937 6	0.917	1.632	0.940 8	0.955 6	2.074	0.903 8	0.892 5	1.134	1.145		

*Value at 301 K.

Density and viscosity values of water and methanol are taken from literature.

tems proves that an ion does not have the same effective radius as expected, due to ion-solvent interaction.

The values are quite high, as expected for highly hydrogen bonded solvents. Both the cation and anion can move through the solutions eventhough the energy required to overcome the viscous force is high. The structure of water determines the Walden product in water-methanol or water-ethanol mixtures. The Walden product of electrolytes in these solvents increases and then decreases passing through a maximum.

The structure-making may be attributed to the positive solvation, and greater slope of the plots of Walden product vs temperature in case of water-methanol than that of water-ethanol, suggests that greater solvation takes place in case of water-methanol. In other words, the order of solvation of CAT by methanol is greater than ethanol. This is what observed experimentally. Similar argument may also hold good for BAT in methanol. Morinaga and Miyaji¹⁷ observed a sharp decrease in the ratio R_x ,

$$R_x = \frac{(\lambda_m^o \eta_o) \text{ solvent mixture}}{(\lambda_m^o \eta_o) \text{ water}} \quad (10)$$

on the addition of non-polar solvent to a polar solvent

mixture, and concluded that this being a strong indication of the selective solvation of the electrolyte or ion by the solvent in these mixtures. In the present case also, the R_x values of the electrolyte in water-alcohol mixtures differ sharply from unity on addition of alcohol, suggesting the preferential solvation of electrolyte or ion by alcohol in these mixtures. The R_x values which are less than unity and their decrease with the addition of a non-polar solvent to water, is also observed by Kalidas *et al.*^{2,5}.

Generally Walden rule holds better for larger and not heavily hydrated ions and hence having more or less the same effective radius in various solvents,

$$\lambda_m^o \eta_o = \frac{1}{6 \pi r T} \quad (11)$$

where r is the effective radius of the ion. Effective radius of $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{NCl}^-$ and Na^+ ions are different for water-methanol compared to water-ethanol.

In the present studies it is thus apparent that the variation of Walden product with solvent compositions are due to electrochemical equilibrium between CAT/BAT ions and the solvent molecules on one hand and the selective solvation of ions on the other with the

composition of mixed solvents.

Experimental

Chloramine-T (G.R., E. Merck) was used. Bromamine-T was prepared and checked for purity¹⁶.

Chloramine-T solution ($\sim 5.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³) in various composition of water-methanol and water-ethanol (v/v) and BAT solution ($\sim 5.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³) of different composition of water-methanol (v/v) mixture were prepared and stored in dark coloured bottles. Double-distilled water (conductivity, $10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) and purified methanol and ethanol were used for preparing various binary mixtures.

Density was measured using a pycnometer (10 cm³ capacity) and viscosity using a Ostwald viscometer (20 cm³). Conductance was measured on an Elico CM-180 conductivity meter having a dip type conductivity cell with platinised electrodes calibrated¹⁸ (cell constant, 0.999cm^{-1}). All the measurements were made in a thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ$).

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